

Security Vulnerabilities In Physical Layer Of Cognitive Radio

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ABSTRACT

Cognitive Radio (CR) with Dynamic Spectrum Access (DSA) is a promising technology to alleviate spectrum shortage problem in wireless communications. Military and commercial interests in the technology are high, to promote greater spectrum efficiency. The CR/DSA radio networking, however, introduces entirely new classes of security threats and providing strong security may prove to be the most difficult aspect of making CR/DSA a viable technology. In this paper, we focus on security vulnerabilities in the physical (PHY) layer of CR/DSA radio networks with energy based spectrum sensing. Various types of threats in PHY layer will be described, a testbed was developed and the results of security assessments on Primary User Emulation attack, Denial of Service attack and Spectrum Honey-pot attack will be presented.

Keywords—Cognitive Radios, CR, Dynamic Spectrum Access, DSA, Primary User, Secondary User, PUE, DoS, Spectrum Honey-pot.

1. INTRODUCTION

Radio electromagnetic spectrum is a precious and limited resource for uses in wireless communications. The current statically allocated model results in an insufficient amount of spectrum to meet the growing demands of both commercial and military users. Studies show that allocated spectrum is often heavily underutilized [1], [2], [3]. Opportunistically reclaiming the unused allocated/licensed spectrum for other applications, without interference to the licensed user (a.k.a Primary User (PU)), has great potential to alleviate spectrum shortage problems. CR/DSA technology was introduced to serve the purpose [4].

As of today, CR is a multi-dimensional awareness, learning and adaptation technology that encompasses, but is not limited to electromagnetic environment (DSA), climate environment, terrain, geolocation, power, modulation, coding and routing. To date, however, most efforts have focused on development and implementation of a DSA engine for CR, such as the DARPA XG and WNaN programs. A DSA engine allows spectrum Secondary Users

(SU) to exploit local and instantaneous spectrum availability on a non-interfering basis and without PU negotiation, thus it provides a means to achieve spectral efficiency and robustness for spectrum dependent systems. A DSA engine can also learn from the electromagnetic environment to establish its environment adaptation policy. Ironically, being capable of adapting also means being capable of being taught by a “bad” instructor with bad information resulting in unintended behavior; e.g. vulnerable to security threats [5]. In this paper, we focus on security vulnerabilities in the PHY layer of CR/DSA networks, specifically on networks that employ energy based spectrum sensing techniques. The remainder of this paper will be organized as follows. Section 2 discusses different types of security threats in PHY layer. Section 3 presents security assessments on specific DSA radios with testing results. Section 4 summarizes the paper.

2. SECURITY THREATS IN PHYSICAL LAYER

The PHY layer in a CR with DSA engine is more complex than a general one because it can dynamically sense and transmit/receive on various frequencies across a frequency spectrum range. In general, security threats to wireless communication networks are classified into two types: outsider threat and insider threat. Outsider threat attempts to inject energy into the targeted network to achieve a desired goal. Insider threat attempts to use its network member status to act as a malicious node to achieve a desired goal. These two types of threat are applicable to both CR and non-CR networks, however, the principal of operation without interference to a PU makes CR/DSA especially vulnerable to injections that produce bad spectrum sensing information.

2.1 Insider Threat

Insider threat, i.e. byzantine threat, is normally a legitimate member of the network and is compromised with malicious intent. In attacking a DSA engine of a CRN, a byzantine node can act as a jammer to control the operating frequency of the CR/DSA network. The frequency spectrum jamming can be achieved with either Physical Jamming or Virtual Jamming.

As a legitimate member of the CR/DSA network, a byzantine node has knowledge of the spectrum sensing algorithm of the network and uses this information to transmit RF signals with the intent to trick the network into believing frequency channels are occupied by PU signals. In a “listen-before-talk” CR/DSA network, all the malicious node needs to do is to transmit during the network’s sensing period as shown in Fig. 1. The DSA engine employs energy sensing scheme but cannot make an accurate distinction between the PU and the malicious transmission [6]. Consequently, the effected CR/DSA radios are tricked into believing that the channel is occupied by PU. Also, by way of spectrum sensing information sharing, the faulty sensing information is spread and indirectly affects other members of the network beyond the RF range of the malicious node.

Fig. 1 – Direct physical jamming attack

Physical RF jamming also could be carried out by the byzantine node in an indirect method in which the infected node transmits spectrum utilization information to an out-of-network jammer, for an external attack. The advantage of this approach is that an out-of-network jammer normally has much more radiated RF power than a byzantine node, hence its effects are broader.

In Virtual Jamming the infected node maliciously alters and spreads spectrum sensing information that indicates channels are not available. This type of attack is more powerful, because it does not require the infected node to have high radiated power.

2.2 Outsider Threat

An outsider threat cannot see the traffic being transmitted in the network. However, with a relatively low level of sophistication, outsider threats can do significant damage to CR/DSA network operation. To negatively effect CR/DSA network operation, outside threats simply inject energy into the CR/DSA network to emulate a Primary User. Outside

threats could also attempt to inject valid messages into CR/DSA networks for spoofing.

3. PHYSICAL RF JAMMING ON DSA ENGINE

Physical RF jamming, from inside or outside, is a serious threat to a CR/DSA networks. It can effect the immediate operations of CR/DSA networks. It can also have long term negative impact on the network, due to the CR’s capability of learn from the environment to establish internal policy constraints. A testbed was setup to study vulnerabilities of DSA engine due to RF jamming. For this study, a network was setup with two DSA enabled radios, one as a Base Station (BS) and the other as a Subscriber Station (SS) UUTs) as depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 – DSA vulnerabilities testing setup

The UUTs employed a power sensing technique for sensing the electromagnetic environment. With this technique, any non-DSA signal, narrowband or wideband that has power larger than the UUTs’ detection threshold is considered as PU. The jammer is composed of electronic surveillance and Electronic Attack (EA) units, a Real-time Spectrum Analyzer (RSA) and a Signal Generator/Arbitrary Waveform Generator (SigGen) that are controlled by a computer.

3.1 PUE Attack

The UUTs continuously sense the spectrum and execute a channel evacuation to vacate the channel upon the return of the channel PU. This spectrum evacuation process, however, can be manipulated by tricking the CR/DSA radios into considering that the channel is occupied by the PU, when it is not. This type of attack is known as a Primary User Emulation (PUE) attack. A DSA engine using the energy detection algorithm is especially vulnerable to a PUE attack. PUE attacks can be carried out with different methods.

Search and Jam – In this test, a 20 MHz bandwidth was set as the frequency sensing band for the UUTs with the UUTs

communicating in a 1.75 MHz bandwidth channel. Controlled by the computer, the RSA continuously senses the 20 MHz bandwidth for the DSA signal. Once the DSA signal is identified, the computer instructs the SigGen to generate a jamming signal (CW signal) in the band of the DSA channel signal. As expected, the UUTs vacate the channel and reestablishes communications on another available channel. The frequency of signal disruption is controlled by the jammer dwell time. The network data throughput was measured to study the effects on the link QoS during the testing. Fig. 3 presents a data set of the testing. As expected, shortening the jammer dwell time (e.g. the more often the DSA channel had to move) reduced the data throughput.

Fig. 3 – Data throughput/packet loss of QAM16 with jamming of: (a) 1sec dwell time; (b): 4 sec dwell time

Cost of network reestablishment – Of course during the time period from the moment the CR/DSA network abandoned a channel to the moment the CR/DSA network started to retransmit on a new channel, data transmission was not available. Furthermore, studies demonstrated that payload transmission was not only stopped during this period but it also suffered during network reestablishment period. The spectrogram in Fig. 4 shows that the UUTs retransmitted RF signal on new channel in only about 11 msec after abandonment of the old channel. However, as shown in Fig. 3, it took much longer than 11 msec for the transmission to resume. This comparison points out costs to the CR/DSA networks resulting from channel migration; specifically it is the cost of the network handshake during a network reestablishment episode. It is obvious that the more often the network has to change frequencies, the more severely data throughput is impacted.

Fig. 4 – CR/DSA spectrogram

3.2 Denial of Service Attack (DoS)

In a DSA context, DoS means denial to spectrum access and it could be achieved in many ways.

DoS with wideband noise – In this method the jammer is a wideband noise source that sends out energy cover the targeted CR/DSA network spectrum sensing bandwidth. In this setup, the power level of the wideband noise was just above the UUTs’ detection threshold (-90dBm). The noise waveform was created on the host computer using a MATLAB script. The waveform was then transferred to an AWG for transmission. Observation showed that as soon as the wideband noise waveform was transmitted, the UUTs blocked out the entire spectrum because it appeared to the DSA that the spectrum was fully occupied.

Fig. 5 – DoS with wideband noise source

DoS with multi-tone signal – With knowledge of CR/DSA channel bandwidth, a multi-tone signal, comb signal, can be created to effectively block out the targeted spectrum bandwidth. In our study, MATLAB script was created to produce a multi-tone waveform over the UUTs sensing bandwidth, 200 MHz. Results indicate that as soon as the tones were transmitted, the UUTs detected the energy and avoided those channels.

Fig. 6 – DoS with multi-tone signal

DoS with sweep jamming – This method requires some knowledge of the targeted DSA algorithm. Once a PU signal channel is detected, a DSA algorithm will normally mark it as unavailable and prevent the DSA from revisiting the channel for a certain time period. Forcing the DSA radio not to revisit an occupied channel for a short time period prevents the DSA radio from continuously attempting rejoining a channel where a primary user is using a form of bursty communication [8]. With knowledge of this channel timeout, sensing bandwidth and channel bandwidth, one can calculate the sweep jammer’s step size and dwell time to control available bandwidth for the CR/DSA network.

For example, a CR/DSA network has channel bandwidth of 2 MHz, sensing bandwidth of 20 MHz and a channel

timeout of 5 seconds, the sweep jammer step size and dwell time can be calculated for different scenarios as following.

Total DoS: Step Size = 2 MHz; No of Step = 20 MHz/2 MHz = 10 steps; Dwell Time = 5 sec/10 Step = 0.5 sec/Step

50% DoS: Dwell Time = 5 sec/5 Step = 1 sec/Step

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 – DoS w/ sweep jamming: (a) 100%; (b) 50% DoS

Without DSA information, “blind” sweep jamming may still effectively degrade QoS of the CR/DSA networks, due to the cost of network formation and network reestablishment as described above.

3.3 Spectrum Honeypot – Spectrum Herding

Spectrum herding using noise: This is done by first creating a wideband noise signal as described in DoS attack. Then a narrowband notch filter is used to create a spectral hole for the DSA radio to operate as shown in Fig. – 8. The UUTs quickly detected the available spectrum and formed the network communication link in the available band.

Fig. 8 – Spectrum herding with noise

Spectrum herding using multi-tone signal: In this case, evenly spaced RF tones are used to block out the spectrum just like the multi-tone attack. Tones at specific frequency are turned off to create the desired frequency spot for operating the CR/DSA radio. With a well controlled operation, sweep jamming can also achieve the same effect.

Fig. 9 – Spectrum herding with multi-tone signal

Results indicate that simple physical RF jamming can produce significant damage to CR/DSA network performance. In literature, counter attack techniques have been proposed such as described in [5], [6], [7], [8] and many others. Efficiencies and feasibilities of proposed counter attack algorithms are the subject for other studies.

4. SUMMARY

In this paper we identified and discussed security vulnerabilities in PHY layer of CR/DSA networks due to physical RF jamming. A testbed was developed and measurements were performed to study the effects of PUE, DoS and Spectrum Herding attacks on CR/DSA networks with energy based spectrum sensing. Data indicates that with a relatively simple level of sophistication, physical RF jamming can significantly degrade CR/DSA networks performance. CR/DSA is a promising technology to meet the ever-increasing spectrum demands in both military and commercial wireless applications; however, the technology introduces entirely new classes of security threats and challenges, especially on spectrum sensing of DSA engine. Counter attack techniques must be developed to make CR/DSA a viable technology for wireless communications.

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